

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

The Interpretive Policy and Practice Analysis Framework

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
IPA	Interpretive Policy Analysis
IPrA	Interpretive Practice Analysis

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Executive Summary

While emotions have been studied in the sphere of politics, their role in policies and policy practices is an under-researched topic (Kuokkanen, 2023). This report presents two interpretive traditions for analysing emotions particularly in the field of policies and policy practices: interpretive (or interpretative) policy analysis (IPA) and interpretive (or interpretative) practice analysis (IPrA). This report was developed in the context of PLEDGE, a Horizon Europe-funded project (Grant Agreement No.: 101132560), in Work Package WP3: Research Framework and Data Management, and more specifically, in Task 3.3: Qualitative Studies under Activity 3.3.4: Interpretative Practice Analysis (IPrA) and Interpretative Policy Analysis (IPA) frameworks. It is addressed mainly to scholars and practitioners wanting to know more about the IPA/IPrA framework developed as a part of PLEDGE, presenting the central elements of this conceptual and methodological framework.

1. Introduction

1.1 About PLEDGE

PLEDGE, a Horizon Europe-funded project (Grant Agreement No.: 101132560), investigates the emotional dynamics driving political grievances and their effects on democratic governance. By bringing together researchers, policymakers, and citizens, the project seeks to deepen our understanding of how emotions shape political behaviour and to develop tools and strategies for fostering emotionally responsive governance and pro-democratic civic engagement. The project has several key objectives: to generate knowledge on the emotional determinants and outputs of anti/pro-democratic grievance politics, to generate practical understanding of how the emotional economy of grievance politics impacts policymaking, and to bring together theory and practice and generate tools promoting effective policymaking and communication which can enhance emotionally intelligent and responsive democratic governance.

1.2 Objectives, targets and methodology of the report

The relationship between emotions and political perspectives has a long history (Plamper, 2015). However, there has recently been an increased interest in the thematic both because of societal developments such as the strengthening of populist movements, affective polarisation, radicalisation and extremism (see, e.g., Bonansinga, 2020), but also because of a broader “affective turn” occurring in the social sciences in the 21st century (Hoggett & Thompson, 2012; Clough & Halley, 2007). In the study of emotions, studies with a positivist or realist perspective consider emotions to be more universal and measurable, while research with an interpretivist perspective emphasises the manifold social, cultural, and historical characteristics of emotions (Plamper, 2015).

While emotions have been studied in the sphere of politics, their role in policies and policy practices is an under-researched topic (Kuokkanen, 2023). This report presents two interpretive traditions for analysing emotions particularly in the field of policies and policy practices: interpretive (or interpretative) policy analysis (IPA) and interpretive (or interpretative) practice analysis (IPrA).

This report was developed in the context of Work Package WP3: Research Framework and Data Management, and more specifically, in Task 3.3: Qualitative Studies under Activity 3.3.4: Interpretive Practice Analysis (IPrA) and Interpretive Policy Analysis (IPA) frameworks.

The IPA-IPrA framework was initially used as an internal framework in the PLEDGE project for the analysis of policy material and social media and as a broader tool for developing interview questionnaires and their analytical scheme. This report is addressed mainly to practitioners and scholars wanting to know more about the IPA/IPrA framework used in PLEDGE, presenting the central elements of this conceptual and methodological framework.

2. IPA as a framework

2.1 The main elements of IPA

Traditional forms of policy analysis are not ideal for capturing the emotional dimension of policymaking, which often require a more interpretive approach. Initially, policy analysis, an applied social science discipline, emerged in the United States in the 1960s and 1970s to provide information about the policymaking process and scientific knowledge to support decision-making on specific policies (Fischer, 2003). The focus of traditional policy analysis on technical expertise and systematically measurable policy outcomes was nevertheless criticised since the 1970s by showing the limits to administration, control, implementation and rationalism (see Fischer, 2003, Hajer & Wagenaar, 2003). IPA, born in the early 2000s, belongs to newer traditions challenging traditional policy analysis.

Rather than a method, IPA is a broad framework or umbrella accommodating various methodological approaches. It is based on three central characteristics (Hajer & Wagenaar, 2003; Wagenaar, 2011). The first of which is *the use of interpretive and primarily qualitative research methods*. Especially in the United States, IPA draws on the criticism of mainstream policy analysis (e.g. Fischer, 2003, Dryzek, 2006). However, in European research, with a stronger tradition of qualitative research (Hill, 2009, p. 10), IPA is less clearly tied to a conflict between positivist and interpretive schools but recognises the coexistence of different forms of research.

A second characteristic of IPA is its close *connection to democratic theory and critical research* (Fischer, 2003; Hajer & Wagenaar, 2003). Born in the aftermath of the Second World War, the initial mission of policy analysis was to contribute to the development of democratic societies (Lasswell & Lerner, 1951). In this context, IPA contributes in particular to the research on new forms of democratic participation and deliberation. It is also interested in “openings” and “closures” in the policy process, with issues being politicised and depoliticised (Hajer & Wagenaar, 2003; see also Glynos & Howarth, 2007).

The third characteristic of IPA is *the blurring of academic and practical forms of knowledge* (Hajer & Wagenaar, 2003; Wagenaar, 2011). IPA is inherently practice-oriented, highlighting the combination of academic and practical knowledge, with an interaction with practitioners, stakeholders and citizens (e.g., Yanow, 2015; Wagenaar, 2011).

In practice, IPA is an umbrella concept for several interpretive approaches. Wagenaar (2011) sees the biggest difference between them in how they understand *meaning* in the process of

interpretation. First, studies can focus on what is hidden “behind” a specific policy through the experiences of policy actors (*hermeneutic meaning*). Second, they can be coupled with discursive and narrative approaches (see also van Hulst et al., 2025), focusing on language use, storylines and the role of language in constructing reality and being inherently coupled to power (*discursive meaning*). Finally, they can highlight practices, everyday experience, dialogue and deliberation with the research participants (*dialogical meaning*). It is nevertheless important to note that these approaches overlap considerably, and they can borrow “tools” and mindsets from each other.

2.2 The analysis process in IPA

The analysis process described below is based on a synthesis of literature on the topic, particularly the works of Wagenaar (2011), Yanow (1993, 2000), Schwartz-Shea and Yanow (2012) and Yanow & Schwartz-Shea (2015).

In the beginning of the research process, the researcher has certain general research questions and a prior understanding of a specific field of study, theories and ways of conducting research. Although strict hypothesis testing is avoided in IPA the researcher may have a “theoretically coloured” idea already in the beginning. However, the research process involves a constant dialogue between theory and the empirical data, in the research literature called as abduction or retroduction (Wagenaar, 2011; Yanow, 1993; Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012; Yanow & Schwartz-Shea 2015).

Central for the interpretive policy analyst is to make sense of specific knowledge around a certain policy issue (Yanow, 2000, 38; see also Schwartz-Shea & Yanow 2012; Yanow & Schwartz-Shea, 2015, Wagenaar, 2011). This includes identifying groups of people who might share understandings of specific policy ideas, which Yanow (2000) calls interpretive communities, and the relevant policy artefacts through which understandings of the policy issue are expressed, both written and verbal. A central aspect is even the meaning that a policy issue has for different audiences (Wagenaar, 2011, 296); thus, focus is even on uniting elements and differences between these interpretive communities (cf. Glynos & Howarth, 2007; Laclau & Mouffe, 1985). The exact terminology used depends on the chosen tradition (e.g., a specific discourse analytical tradition).

IPA draws on several forms of data and methods of data collection, such as the analysis of written policy documents and semi-structured qualitative interviews, but even ethnographic participant observation (Yanow, 2000; Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012; Wagenaar, 2011). The

different types of data can be used separately in combination, with a focus to read “across” the material rather than treating it as separate (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012).

The data analysis has the aim of moving from empirical material to generalisations, often through coding (Wagenaar, 2011) and close reading (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012). In the interpretation of the data, IPA includes two forms of interpretations: the self-interpretations of the research participants (such as the interviewees or contents of the policy documents) and the interpretations of the researcher. The researcher must take seriously the self-interpretations of the actors engaged in the practice under study, but at the same time have the capacity to see beyond them (Glynos and Howarth, 2007).

The analysis process must nevertheless leave room for puzzles and surprises, or findings that can contradict the initial assumptions of the researcher, are contradictory or require further inquiry (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012; Yanow & Schwartz-Shea, 2015; Glynos & Howarth, 2007; Yanow, 2000). The researcher should see this as a relevant result leading to new questions and ways to theorise the findings according to the underlying research logic of abduction (or retroduction).

3. IPrA as a framework

3.1 The main elements of IPrA

Like IPA, IPrA, also known in International Relations as *practice theory*, is a methodological-theoretical approach rather than a method per se. It involves the simultaneous use of different methods towards a common goal and spans practical and analytical spaces that no single method can capture entirely (Pouliot, 2012, p. 55). IPrA is based on a broader theoretical background of “constructivist structuralism”. It draws particularly strongly on the research framework developed by the French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu and has been applied broadly in social and political sciences, for instance in the study of international relations (Kauppi, 2003; Nair, 2024; Adler-Nissen, 2008, 2012; Bueger, 2016; Pouliot, 2010).

The goal of IPrA is to apprehend how practices, spaces, social relations and power become historically co-constituted. The “entry” to this complex network happens through the multi-methodological interpretation of practices in political spaces. According to IPrA, social relations and processes tend to manifest in two ways: in bodies (or “habitus”) and things (or “field”).

Practice refers to the meaning-making processes emerging at the intersection of habitus and field. Habitus are the unconscious, “embodied inclinations acquired through exposure and experience in various positions and games”. (Pouliot, 2012, p. 48). An actor’s habitus is operationalised as dispositions (ingrained and inarticulate proclivities and tendencies accumulated through personal exposure and collective history). Field refers to the social spaces with their own rules, where actors compete for resources and power (i.e., corresponding to social structures). An actor’s field is operationalised as positions, which are defined by the distribution of valued resources inside a “social game” (e.g., EU policymaking). Finally, IPrA uses the concept of capital: the resources (e.g., social, financial, economic, cultural, etc.) and stakes upon which struggle(s) and fields are formed.

The utility of IPrA lies in its interpretation of practices through the careful and entangled analysis of situations, dispositions, and positions. In other words: “practices are, at once, positional and dispositional” (Pouliot, 2012, p. 48). For IPrA, an agent’s dispositions are “historical traces of them occupying various positions in the past” (ibid., p. 47), which help make sense of certain practices both shaping and shaped by the field and habitus of the actor and those they affect. What it is important to understand in this instance is that “Social spaces do not ‘cause’ practices but rather account for them by mapping the social terrains on which they are being performed.” (ibid., p. 55).

However, dispositions never perfectly map onto positions because of i) uncertainty, crisis, or otherwise the unexpected and uncontrollable; ii) the combination of the trajectories of different fields (e.g., seen in their cultural diversities). Moreover, positional logics equally do not account for practices on their own.

3.2 The analysis process in IPrA

IPrA studies the practices of key actors under the logics of position (i.e., the actor's position in the field) and disposition (i.e., their habitus within the field). These logics give practices their shape, meanings and social efficacy.

Due to the complexity of analysing habitus, field, and practice, IPrA is designed more as a methodological approach than a strict method. Practices involve analysing both historical or political structures and mechanisms (e.g., the division and rules of coalition forming in the European Parliament) shaping power – i.e., the social space or fields – and the lived/embodied experience of these historical/political structures in actors reinforcing or resisting power – i.e. habitus.

For example, if we want to interrogate how MEPs consider (and experience) the grievances and emotions of both its constituents and the larger body politic, we need to consider their positions within a social structure shaping their meaning-making practices. Methodologically, this means simultaneously: i) analysing the structural space in which they operate (distribution of resources and capital in the field determining their position), ii) exploring their dispositional spaces (sets of embodied histories and trajectories), and iii) analysing their practical spaces (found in interactions in everyday life). No single method can capture these distinct ontologies. Consequently, IPrA can be ideally (but not necessarily) developed by rather large groups of researchers with different skills and expertise working together.

IPrA, in short, can be operationalised in a three-step research strategy focusing on a different aspect of practices: getting access to practices; reconstructing dispositional logics of practices; and constructing positional logics of practices. These three steps will be presented more in detail below.

3.2.1 Getting access to practices

The first step consists of getting *access to practices*. The objective is to map the local space of practices and their situational unfolding. Practices are raw data, forming the empirical entry point to empirical analysis. However, direct access to practices is very difficult, which requires imagining and combining methodological proxies (as well as their merits and limits).

Ideally, the access to practices would be done through ethnographical participant observation (direct observation in “natural habitat”); however, this method is very difficult, lengthy, and resource-intensive. More realistically, accessing practices requires a combination of methods. When practices cannot be “seen” (the “ideal” scenario, i.e. participant observation) they can be “talked about” (e.g. interviews, focus groups) or accessed by “reading” (e.g., policy documents; see Pouliot, 2012, pp. 48–50).

Broadly speaking, using IPrA in interviews involves the recounting, description, and recreation the policymakers’ “everyday”. There are four ways to use interviews to analyse practices:

- Ask interviewees to *recount* their everyday practices – by which means they accomplish a task; their daily schedule; who, how, and where they meet. These questions aim at reconstructing the practical space
- Ask interviewees to *describe* the practices of others/their colleagues. This turns interviewee into a participant observer.
- *Recreate* part of the practical context via focus groups, which allow to identify more “natural” patterned, meaningful gestures in the group.
- *Treat* interviews as performances or practices: see how actors relate to the interviewer and the interview itself (framing, presentation) since a/their world (field) is performed into being.

As noted above, practices can also be accessed by “reading” (i.e. textual analysis). This can be done in two ways:

- *Select* diverse textual genres offering a window into practices (yet in different fashion): e.g., memoirs, court cases, handbooks, etc.
- *Treat* discourse as practice. Importantly, for IPrA scholars (including Bourdieu) “discourse” in this framework is performative (i.e., language not only describes but shapes social reality and its power/domination structures). The meaning put into texts is a rich (even inexhaustible) source of historical and emotional traces (Pouliot, 2012,

p. 49). However, discourse analysis alone can be insufficient to understand the practical logics that go into practices.

Finally, “observing”, “talking about” and “reading” can also be used in various combinations, for instance in the analysis of social media interactions.

3.2.2 Reconstructing dispositional logics of practices

When reconstructing dispositional logics of practices, the core question is: “What would the actor need to know to grasp the meaning of a gesture [“insider meanings that agents attribute to their reality”] in terms of how it affects and is affected by the world?” (Pouliot, 2012, p. 50). In other terms, what tacit “know-how” do actors need to grasp the “game” [the logic of the sociopolitical space]? Thus, it is crucial that the researcher does not impose scientific categories over the observed and rather tries to recover “practical meanings” and “common-sense” (ibid.).

Reconstructing dispositional logics can follow a three-step process (what Pouliot calls “subjectivity”):

1. Inductive recovery of agents’ realities and practical logics: Often, the ethnographic participant observation of the agents in their “natural habitat” (leading to the interpretive inference of the tacit “know-how” that compose practices) is difficult. Consequently, the task of the researcher is to locate and operate from the “nearest possible vantage point” (Pouliot, 2012, p. 51). This ethnographic sensibility (e.g., deployed in interviews or narrative analysis of official and informal content) is particularly relevant considering the difficulties in unearthing the role of emotions on key political actors.
2. Objectification of these realities and practical logics through the interpretation of intersubjective contexts (prominently, their relations with others and other practices/institutions). Here, textual analysis (from social media posts to memoirs and cases) should be done considering this “ethnographic sensibility” (ibid.), which can illuminate both practices and the practical knowledge bound to these practices.

The analysis can focus on the resources wielded (for instance, in the discursive configuration of specific policies) or inferring assumptions from statements (e.g.,

“people are anxious / fearful / angry about Russia’s invasion of Ukraine”). These analyses help to understand what underlines agent’s thinking and actions.

Interviews are well suited for reconstructing practitioners PoV (Point of View) – particularly good for analysing the role of emotions. However, the impact of reflexivity about emotions and emotional states should be carefully considered. A specific methodological challenge is that practical knowledge (in contrast to representational knowledge, which explicit, e.g., theoretical understandings) is unsaid and tacit. “Forcing” the interviewee to reflect on the tacit practice implies a loss in addressing practical knowledge.

3. Historicization of realities and practical logics (the historical origins of these features). It is critical to note that interviews are more than interpreting the practitioners PoV: We also need to locate, in the social space, the position from which interviewees express their views (here, for instance “historical biographies” could be suitable method, as well as different forms of textual analysis).

3.2.3 Constructing positional logics of practices

Finally, the construction of the positional logic of practices involves three tasks:

1. Interpreting the rules of the game: To interpret the intersubjective rules of the game, we need to reconstruct the implicit beliefs shaping social practices (doxa) of a given field by interpreting practices through diverse texts. Discourse analysis here becomes the key method with which to address and analyse the doxa/given rules. Besides discursive practices, texts provide access to rules inscribed in diverse social artefacts (codes, symbols, objects, committees, resources) that structure the field.
2. Map the distribution of resources: The analysis of positional logic also relates to the distribution of resources (e.g., social, cultural, financial, technological, etc.) and players (e.g., different types of civil servants, different levels of political representatives, etc.) across space (Pouliot, 2012, pp. 53–54). The methodological focus here should be on revealing and analysing the relations between various social artefacts and classifications to search for patterns invisible at the action level (ibid., p. 54). Various methods can be used for this mapping, including statistical ones such as correspondence analysis, which allows visualising a two-dimensional representation

of the inter-relationship among multiple sets of elements, or social network analysis (ibid, pp. 54–55).

3. Historicise social struggles: The construction of positional logic requires methods to introduce historicity and social genesis. The field's doxa (i.e., the assumptions and the taken-for-granted beliefs) can be historicized by reconstituting its evolution over time, including contestations and dislocations (cf. Foucault's genealogy or historical/critical discourse analysis).

4. Combining IPA and IPrA in the study of emotions in policies and policy practices

4.1 General viewpoints

When applying IPA into the study of emotions in policies, it must be seen as “integral” and used as a “lens” in the analysis, not just as an add-on (Durnová, 2022). The emotions studied are understood both as individual and collective ones (Durnová, 2015). They can be both those of policymakers and those affected by policies, either directly addressed by them or, when studying policy material produced by policymakers, analysed through references to people’s emotions in this material. The policy settings studied can be both more conflictual and more consensus-oriented (Barnes, 2012; Durnová, 2015). In this context, emotions provide information on what matters, which issues are controversial and what consequences (both intended and unintended) policies can have on various groups of people (Durnová, 2022; see also Meriluoto & Kuokkanen, 2022). However, references to emotions can also be used in the policy context as a tool for power, for instance when framing certain viewpoints as “irrational” or “too emotional” (Flyvbjerg, 1998; Meriluoto & Kuokkanen, 2022). As a general umbrella framework, IPA, is frequently combined with other qualitative and interpretive traditions, such as discourse, narrative and frame analyses (van Hulst et al., 2025), giving more specific tools to analyse emotions in discourses, narratives or policy frames.

Through the access to practices and the analysis of dispositional and positional logics, IPrA contributes to understanding the role of emotions within the context of policymaker's practices in two co-constituted dimensions: i) policymakers' views about (and relation to) their constituents and other EU residents/citizens' emotional demands, needs, and expectations in terms of habitus and capital; and ii) policymakers' own emotions as part of their historically-coded yet unfixed (and unconscious) habitus, which are mutually-shaped with a professional/sociopolitical field constantly re-constituting through social conflict/struggle.

As frameworks, IPA and IPrA share joint characteristics: an interpretive perspective, a focus on practices, a stepwise research process and both being broad frameworks or “lenses” rather than strict methods. The more general framework of IPA makes it easy to combine it with interpretive practice analysis (IPrA), which focuses on the interpretation of the policy practices using another terminology. Although IPA has been used in various policy contexts, in combination with several methods and with multiple forms of data, the addition of IPrA to IPA may also help to switch IPA’s perspective from often very local policy processes to broader

(and often, more international) policy practices (Kauppi, 2003; Nair, 2024; Adler-Nissen, 2008, 2012).

4.2 The PLEDGE perspective

For the practical use of the IPA and IPrA frameworks, the researcher can borrow one or several elements from research processes described above, adapted more detailed to the specific study and method in question (e.g., interviews, focus groups, document analysis). As general frameworks, both IPA and IPrA also allow flexibility in their application as long as the research has an interpretive, practical and policy-oriented perspective. In the context of IPA, it is good to note that this perspective is also frequently combined with other qualitative and interpretive traditions, such as discourse, narrative and frame analyses (van Hulst et al., 2025). Consequently, IPA can also be used in combination with these analysis traditions, also central in PLEDGE.

In the PLEDGE project, the IPA/IPrA framework were used both in the analysis of written policy material – such as debates in the European Parliament, State of the Union speeches, addresses of national politicians in the EU context, EU regulation, European External Action Service and European Union Advisory Mission press releases, public statements and national action plans. It also used the EP election data gathered elsewhere as a part of PLEDGE and collaborating projects (see Palonen et al. 2025), contributing to the cross-national social media analysis. Finally, the IPA/IPrA framework was used when developing a more general interview framework for the project. Thematically, the IPA and IPrA frameworks were particularly applied for the analysis of grievance-ridden policy areas (climate/energy policy and the war in Ukraine; in this context, primarily analysed with a combination of IPA with discourse and narrative analyses) and for the analysis of policy documents and MEP election campaigns in the context of the war in Ukraine.

In terms of how the two frameworks worked together, IPA served as the initial analytical entry point. It guided the identification of interpretive communities, policy artefacts, and the discursive and narrative patterns through which emotional governance takes shape in the collected material (Yanow, 2000; van Hulst et al., 2025). IPrA was then brought in to deepen the analysis, focusing on what those patterns reveal about the field positions, habitus, and capital of the actors producing them. Material like a council conclusion or an MEP's social media post was thus read at two levels: what it communicates discursively, and what it suggests about the structural and dispositional conditions shaping its production.

This two-level approach proved productive in the social media analysis, where IPA's sensitivity to narrative framing and discursive sequences worked alongside IPrA's positional logic to explain why EMSoS (Emotional Mechanism of Solidarity-Oriented Sharing) and EMRes (Emotional Mechanism of Ressentiment) dynamics (see Capelos et al., 2024) took different forms in the countries analysed in the EP2024 social media analysis developed by UH (Palonen, 2025) — differences that reflect the specific institutional locations and political trajectories of the actors involved.

The initial analysis using the IPA-IPrA framework on policy documents and social media data (EP2024 election data) points to a consistent tension between regulatory and emotional registers across EU institutional material, as well as social media audiovisual material. Official policy documents (regulations, Council conclusions, Commission communications) rely predominantly on technical and procedural language, with emotional content largely implicit but yet present in a language of condemnation, commitment, action and urgency. More direct emotional governance emerges in speeches, official statements, EP debates, and EEAS communications, where themes of solidarity, urgency, sacrifice, and (particularly in the case of the war in Ukraine) moral condemnation of Russian aggression are prominent. EP debates are particularly rich, offering the only institutional space where oppositional emotional framings – primarily from far-right and left-wing groups – are visible alongside the dominant pro-EU narrative. The analysis of the EP2024 election social media data reveals distinct national patterns in EMSoS and EMRes dynamics, particularly in the case of the war in Ukraine, further contributing to the emotional landscape of EU policies. In the analysis of interview material, the IPA/IPrA framework functioned as a more general “lens” when developing the interview questions and the analytical scheme.

On a practical note, applying both frameworks to textual and audiovisual material required a departure from PLEDGE’s original deductive coding scheme developed for interview analysis, while not entirely negating the latter’s analytical contributions. The analysis became progressively more inductive and abductive, iterating between the empirical material and the frameworks' core concepts, with inter-reader reliability sustained through regular team review of analytical decisions. The central themes guiding the analysis are listed in the Table 1 in Annex 1 below.

5. Conclusions

This report presented a conceptual-methodological framework based on two interpretive traditions for analysing emotions particularly in the field of policies and policy practices, IPA and IPrA, based on the existing methodological literature and developed further as a part of the PLEDGE research project. The framework responded to a gap in PLEDGE’s methodological toolkit: existing approaches to emotion in policymaking have relied predominantly on deductive, quantitative instruments that are well suited to survey and experimental data, but limited in their capacity to capture the tacit, practice-embedded, and historically-situated dimensions of emotional governance. IPA and IPrA were adopted to address this gap, providing an interpretive foundation for the analysis of policy material and hybrid media data across the project’s three core crisis contexts (with particular attention to the war in Ukraine and climate change/energy crisis).

Both IPA and IPrA share joint characteristics: an interpretive perspective, a focus on practices, a stepwise research process and both being broad frameworks or “lenses” rather than strict methods. In PLEDGE, IPA served as the initial analytical entry point, guiding the identification of interpretive communities, policy artefacts, and the discursive and narrative patterns through which emotional governance takes shape in the collected material (Yanow, 2000; van Hulst et al., 2025). IPrA deepened the analysis, focusing on what those patterns revealed about the field positions, habitus, and capital of the actors producing them.

The report makes two main contributions. Internally, the IPA-IPrA framework has served as a shared analytical foundation across PLEDGE, informing both the analysis of policy documents and social media material and the development of interview questionnaires and coding schemes. Externally, it offers a replicable methodological model for scholars seeking to study emotional governance in EU policymaking through interpretive means, particularly in contexts where direct access to practitioners is limited.

The principal methodological constraints concerned the adaptation of IPrA, designed around ethnographic access to practices, to a document-based research setting. The application of IPrA to textual material is an inherent compromise, leading the researchers to employ the policy material as proxies for practice and understanding the concept of practices in a broad manner. A further challenge arose from the relatively deductive emotional coding scheme developed for analysing interview data, based on PLEDGE’s conceptual handbook (Capelos et al., 2024), which needed modification for the inductive, practice-oriented logic demanded by IPA and IPrA (see Appendix 1). Future studies could both develop creative alternatives for

accessing practices and develop further interpretive coding protocols for the analysis of emotions.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Coding Scheme for IPA/IPrA in PLEDGE [19 April 2026]

Table 1 – Coding Scheme for IPA/IPrA in PLEDGE [19 April 2026]

Theme	Clarification
Policy domain	The policy domain of the document
Producer/ Speaker	Who has produced the document or who is speaking (in the case of speeches)?
Level of emotions	What is the level of emotions in the document?
General comments on emotional governance	The coder's general comments regarding emotional governance in the document
General comments on discourses or narratives	The coder's more general comments regarding discourses or narratives in the document
General comments on (policy) practices	General comments on (policy) practices
References to anxieties	Are there references to anxieties in the document? In this case, what kind of anxieties?
References to grievances	Are there references to grievances in the document? In this case, what kind of grievances?
References to resentment or EMRes	References to resentment or EMRes: Are there direct references to resentment or to the more complex emotional mechanism of resentment (EMRes) in the document?
References to solidarity or EMSos	Are there direct references to solidarity or to the more complex emotional mechanism of emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing (EMSos) in the document?
References to (other) emotions	Are there other references to emotions in the document? In this case, which emotions?
References to emotional needs	Are there references to emotional needs in the document? In this case, what types of emotional needs?
References to (dis)trust	Are there references to (dis)trust in the document? In this case, what types of references?
References to actors as guilty/responsible	Are there references to actors presented as guilty or responsible for a specific political outcome or policy (N.B. includes also notifying of the actor's own guilt/responsibility)? In this case, who is referred to and in which context?
Crediting actors	Are there references to crediting actors for doing something particularly good/well in the document? In this case, who is credited and in which context?

References to victims or people suffering from political decisions or policies	Are there references to victims or people suffering from political decisions or policies in the document? In this case, who is referred to and in which context?
References to (need for) democratic innovations	Are there references to (the need for) democratic innovations in the document? What types of democratic innovations?
References to gender	Are there references to gender in the document? In which context?
References to action	Are there references to action in the document? What type of action? In which context? (e.g. “The EU needs to do more”)
References to broader ideologies or principles (belief systems)	Are there references to broader ideologies or principles (cf. belief systems) in the document? What types of ideologies or principles?
References to prospects (gains/losses)	Are there references to prospects (particularly the weighing of gains or losses against each other) in the document?
References to status/power	Are there references to status or power in the document? In what ways?
Communicating to other actors	Is the aim of the document to communicate to other actors or does it include communication to them? In what ways?
References to national politicians/policies	Does the document include references to national politicians or policies? Who or which?
References to temporality	Does the document include references to temporality (e.g. long term vs. short term)
Other comments	Other comments by the coders
Illustrative quotes	Particularly illustrative quotes in the document